

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF IMPROVING A WORD STOCK IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

As you broaden your range of vocabulary, you become better able to describe specific settings, emotions, and ideas. You also hone a skill that's known among writers as "painting with words." The most valuable vocabulary words are those that you can recall and use almost automatically.

Key words: complex words, mnemonics, use dictionaries, memory process

INTRODUCTION

Adding new terms to your written vocabulary is one of the simplest methods to improve your existing writing skills. Because the English language is one of the most extensive of all languages, you'll never run out of vocabulary words to learn and utilize. A strong vocabulary benefits all genres of writing, from fiction to journalism to essay writing to poetry. As a result, the time you spend working on your vocabulary is actually time spent working on your writing skills. A writing vocabulary, like a speaking vocabulary, is made up of terms you can quickly recall and utilize. A strong vocabulary supports precise writing and helps you avoid unclear phrases, from action words to descriptive words and beyond.

As you broaden your range of vocabulary, you become better able to describe specific settings, emotions, and ideas. You also hone a skill that's known among writers as "painting with words." The most valuable vocabulary words are those that you can recall and use almost automatically. After all, learning vocabulary is only valuable if you can actually use your new words in a piece of writing and—equally important—use them correctly. If you ask a published author for writing tips, you'll likely be told that it's better to correctly use common words than to incorrectly use complex words. Fortunately, a key benefit of a better vocabulary is being able to use both common *and* complex words with equal

precision. Most of us have not spent much time learning new vocabulary since we were high school or college students. Thankfully you can always pick up where you left off.

METHODS AND DISCUSSION

As Nation (2001) points out that there are three processes, occur when the students successfully remember the words being learnt; noticing, retrieval, and generative use. In this sense, noticing refers to drawing full attention to the lexical item and studying the word, while retrieval means that to retrieve the words that have been noticed to use them creatively. In this sense, the more frequently the words occur, the more memorable the words are. According to Melton (1963) as cited in Mcdermott & Roediger (2016), three necessary stages in the learning and memory process are encoding, storage, and retrieval. Encoding refers to the initial presentation of information; storage is organizing the words in the mental lexicon, while retrieval refers to accessing stored information. In the light of vocabulary learning, retrieval is one of the psychological processes to help the students remember the words; it is initiated by noticing process and followed by generative use of words. According to Baddeley (1990), retrieval can be productive and receptive. When the learners retrieve the meaning of words form that they meet during listening or reading, it is called receptive retrieval. According to Barcroft (2007), when the learners generate the items on their own, it also can lead to the positive effect of the words' retrieval on their memory since before using the words generatively, the learners are required to retrieve the words. In line with that, McNamara & Healy (1995) point out that the generative process can promote the students' cognitive ability which enables them to connect the words to their previous knowledge in order to strengthen their words knowledge. The more frequently they retrieve the words, the easier the recall of the words will be later on. Nation argues that repeated encounters of the words can increasingly facilitate retrieval of the words which make the students remember them. Consistent with this, Webb (2007) finds out that the learners can gain greater knowledge about the

words as repetition of the words is increased. His study implies that if the learners encounter the same words frequently, the bigger opportunity to develop their knowledge about those words. Furthermore, Schmitt (2000) coins that the teachers should not present the words once and forget about it at the next meeting, but repeatedly present and reintroduce them over and over.

RESULTS

Here are some tips to help you start learning new vocabulary words:

Develop a reading habit. Vocabulary building is easiest when you encounter words in context. Seeing words appear in a novel or a newspaper article can be far more helpful than seeing them appear on vocabulary lists. Not only do you gain exposure to unfamiliar words; you also see how they're used. **Use the dictionary and thesaurus.** Online dictionaries and thesauruses are helpful resources if used properly. They can jog your memory about synonyms that would actually be better words in the context of what you're writing. A full dictionary definition can also educate you about antonyms, root words, and related words, which is another way to learn vocabulary. **Play word games.** Classic games like Scrabble and Boggle can function as a fun way to expand your English vocabulary. Crossword puzzles can as well. If you really want to be efficient, follow up rounds of these word games with a little note-taking. Keep a list of the different words you learned while playing the game, and then study that list from time to time. **Use flashcards.** A quick way to build a large vocabulary is to study a number of words via flashcards. In today's digital age, a wide array of smartphone apps make flashcards convenient and easy to organize. **Subscribe to "word of the day" feeds.** Some web platforms will provide you with a word a day—either on a website, an app, or via email—to help you expand your vocabulary. You can add these words to running word lists. **Use mnemonics.** A mnemonic device is a form of word association that helps you remember words' definitions and proper uses. For instance think of the word *obsequious* which means "attempting to win favor from influential

people by flattery.” Break down that word into components: “obse” is the beginning of “obsessed,” “qui” sounds like the French word for “yes” (oui), and “us” is like the word “us.” So you can think of that big word *obsequious* as “obsessed with saying yes to us”—which is kind of what it means! **Practice using new words in conversation.** It’s possible to amass a huge vocabulary without actually knowing how to use words. This means you have to take it upon yourself to put your personal dictionary into use. If you come across an interesting word in your reading, make a point of using it in conversation. By experimenting in low-stakes situations, you can practice the art of word choice and, with a little bit of trial and error, hone in on the right word for a particular context. With 2,500 to 3,000 words, you can understand 90% of everyday English conversations, English newspaper and magazine articles, and English used in the workplace. The remaining 10% you’ll be able to learn from context, or ask questions about. However, it’s essential to learn the right English vocabulary words, so you don’t waste your time trying to memorize a huge collection with very little benefit. **Watch Shows in that Language** Our hearing is a marvelous thing – and the more we hear something, the likelier we are to remember it. You’ll be surprised how you can learn even a language as complicated as Japanese by simply watching shows in that language. The same thing applies to English, and any other language. The more you watch the show, the more you will be able to learn as you are listening – and the good news is that you’ll be learning without even noticing. If you don’t have any shows that you’d like in that particular language, one good alternative here would be to watch the movie or TV show in your language, but to set the subtitles in the language that you want to learn. This way, you will be hearing the movie in the language that you know, and then you will be associating the words with the audio of the movie. The more you do it, the more you will be able to drill those words into your vocabulary. **Learn Phrases** You may want to **improve vocabulary** word by word, but sometimes, it is much easier to learn the phrase rather than the word itself. Go for the more common

phrases first – find out which are the most likely to be used in a conversation. When you put it that way, you will be able to remember it with much more ease. Simply put, when you put those words in a frame, it should be much easier for you to learn them by association. You will hear the word coming before it, and then automatically your brain will think about the word coming after it. These combinations should help you remember the language more easily. **Listen to Music in That Language** New languages are a bit more difficult to learn when you only put them in a theoretical manner. It may seem interesting, but to many, it is just boring – which is why the information might go right past you. This is why you may want to learn a language through something you love – for example, music. You may easily **memorize words** when you do so through music. Ask most of the rock music enthusiasts that learned German by listening to Rammstein. The catchier the song, the likelier you are to remember the lyrics – and therefore, the words. And let's face it; when you see that it's easier to remember song lyrics rather than a person's name, it's clear why this would be a good option for you to learn vocabulary words.

CONCLUSION

In the end, a new language cannot be learned overnight. You need to practice enough until that language becomes stuck in your brain. The more you practice with your vocabulary, the better you should be able to learn. No matter if you choose to learn through a TV show, flashcard, or an app such as Vocab Chat, you need to give it enough of your time to do so. Learning is ceaseless. You can cultivate an erudite persona as an adolescent--or even as an octogenarian--by building your vocabulary. Creating habits to help you learn and use the most accurate words in your language will make it easier to communicate, write, and think.

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